

IP4OS

M3 Campaign Strategy

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1. Summary

Intellectual Property (IP) and Open Science (OS) are essential to fostering innovation, ensuring FAIR scientific knowledge, and enabling sustainable economic, societal, environmental and digital development. However, balancing the management and principles of IP and OS remains challenging for many researchers, institutions, policymakers and businesses.

The **IP4OS project** aims to empower multi-professional teams—including knowledge transfer professionals, data stewards, librarians, research managers, researchers and OS ambassadors—by providing them with the **awareness, knowledge, skills, and advocacy** needed to navigate the complexities of IP and OS in their organisations. By equipping these professionals with the right tools and insights, IP4OS contributes to an ecosystem where Research and Innovation (R&I) are supported, and IP is used responsibly and strategically within the OS framework. IP4OS is launching a comprehensive, gender-balanced **Role Model Campaign** designed to strengthen collaboration and understanding of a synergetic IP-OS approach among academia, industry, policymakers, and social innovators. The project aims to develop a **Synergy Framework**, sharing best practices of agile IP management to support OS practices, highlighting key findings and success stories, and assessing the effectiveness of various IP tools. This will be achieved through diverse communication channels to foster community engagement, particularly within the European Union. The campaign strategy builds on existing European initiatives and awareness-raising efforts led by the European Commission (EC), European Patent Office (EPO), European Union Intellectual Property Office (EUIPO), European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA), and the European IP Helpdesk.

2. Vision

The **IP4OS project envisions a complementary application of IP management and OS practices in the European Research Area (ERA)**. This balance unlocks innovation and reliable research and fosters **sustainable changes** that benefit society and the economy across Europe.

3. Mission

IP4OS will empower multi-professional teams—including researchers, knowledge transfer professionals, data stewards, librarians, research managers, and OS ambassadors—with **awareness, knowledge, skills, and advocacy to unpack the possibilities of IP complementing OS** in their organisations. These multi-professional teams will learn how to **inform and train** their communities to ensure the best use of IP in OS environments.

4. Diagnosis: Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities & Threats (SWOT)

The **IP4OS project** operates in a complex R&I landscape where OS is increasingly prioritised, but the role of **IP in OS remains insufficiently defined**. To ensure the campaign's effectiveness, assessing the campaign's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats is essential, allowing for a strategic and well-targeted approach.

4.1. Strengths

One of the key strengths of the IP4OS project is its **multi-channel approach** to disseminating information. By leveraging a combination of digital platforms, academic networks, and policy dialogues, the IP4OS campaign ensures that its messaging reaches diverse professional groups, from researchers and technology transfer officers to policymakers and industry stakeholders (see box 3, p.9 of Part B of the DoA in the GA).

Another major strength is a **careful selection of the role models** who will champion IP4OS principles. These role models will represent **diverse disciplines, career levels, and professional backgrounds**, making them relatable and effectively engaging different communities. IP4OS will enhance its credibility and broaden its reach by showcasing inclusivity and diversity, ensuring the campaign resonates across various R&I sectors.

Additionally, **existing IP and OS networks** provide a valuable foundation for the campaign.

The Campaign Strategy will be developed based on the existing European initiatives and awareness-raising campaigns of the EC, EPO, EUIPO, EISMEA and the European IP Helpdesk.

National IP offices and OS advocacy groups already offer guidance on IP rights (IPR). By integrating and collaborating with these networks, IP4OS can **build upon established frameworks** and avoid duplicating efforts.

4.2. Weaknesses

Despite these strengths, the initiative faces several challenges. One notable weakness is the **lack of clear Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to measure the campaign's impact**. Without well-defined metrics, tracking progress, evaluating effectiveness, and making data-driven adjustments will be difficult. Establishing quantifiable goals will be crucial in demonstrating the value and success of IP4OS.

Another challenge is **fragmented stakeholder engagement**. While some research communities, such as knowledge transfer professionals and legal experts, may actively engage with IP-related discussions, others—particularly scientists accustomed to OS—may see IP as a **secondary concern**. This perception could hinder participation and adoption of IP4OS principles.

Moreover, **the limited visibility of IP within OS policies** creates an additional barrier. While OS frameworks, such as those developed (i.e. CoARA, EOSC, FAIR Data Principles, Citizen Science, Open Access Mandates, Research Career Competency Models, Institutional OS Policies) under the **European Research Area (ERA)** (i.e. ERA Action 3 Research assessment reform promoting OS, Action 8 Federated OS infrastructure, Action 8, 17 Embedded in EOSC and Horizon Europe, Action 15 Engaging public in research; policy toolkits, Action 2 Includes OS skills, Action 9 Promoted through model policies and incentives) strongly promote open access and data sharing, they often lack structured **guidance on managing IP responsibly within OS environments**. This gap makes it more challenging to position IP4OS as an essential element of the **OS** movement.

4.3. Opportunities

IP4OS has significant opportunities to make an impact by **targeting the right stakeholders with precise outreach strategies**. Developing structured plans for engaging key audiences—such as research institutions, funding agencies, and innovation hubs—through **tailored blog posts, media articles, and digital campaigns** will help strengthen the project's visibility and credibility.

Additionally, IP4OS can strengthen its approach by **leveraging international scientific organisations and research councils**. Institutions such as the **International Science Council (ISC) in Paris** have already explored global research collaboration and knowledge-sharing strategies. By engaging with these organisations, IP4OS will position itself as a key advocate for **integrating IP considerations into international OS policies**.

Another opportunity lies in learning from past OS initiatives that effectively integrated IP considerations. The COVID-19 pandemic, for example, served as a unique case study in global research collaboration. Pharmaceutical companies, such as Pfizer and Moderna, worked with research institutions like the National Institutes of Health (NIH) to share data rapidly and collaborate on vaccine development, navigating IP concerns through mechanisms like the COVAX initiative. By analysing these models, IP4OS can extract best practices and provide practical guidance on how to align IP with open science in ways that benefit both researchers and society.

Global OS initiatives, such as the **Open Source Malaria project in India, the Canadian Open Drug Discovery initiative, Project TRIDENT, and Project Conscience**, demonstrate how different regions and projects balance knowledge sharing and **IP protection**.

For example, the **Open Source Malaria project** has encouraged collaboration among researchers worldwide by providing open access to drug development data, while still ensuring that contributors retain IP rights to their discoveries (<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC5084075/>).

Project TRIDENT, a large transdisciplinary initiative, aims to build an open science preclinical platform for neurodegenerative diseases, examining both the incentives for participating in open science partnerships and how researchers share knowledge across disciplines (<https://www.tridentpreclinicaltrials.org/>).

Project Conscience, a non-profit initiative supported by the Government of Canada, is establishing an open science drug discovery network across Canada. This project has advanced antibiotic research by promoting open data sharing while ensuring that the intellectual property generated is managed under specific frameworks designed to benefit public health. These initiatives offer valuable lessons for IP4OS in crafting globally applicable strategies that foster responsible IP management, enhance accessibility, ensure security, and drive innovation (https://conscience.ca/wp-content/newfold-page-cache/_index.html, <https://www.canada.ca/en/innovation-science-economic-development/news/2023/10/government-of-canada-invests-in-new-open-science-drug-discovery-network.html>).

4.4. Threats

Despite these opportunities, several risks could hinder the effectiveness of IP4OS. One of the main concerns is the difficulty of **reaching and engaging the right stakeholders**. This fragmented stakeholder engagement, as mentioned above in point 4.2 under Weakness,

could escalate into a more significant threat. Some professional groups may be **unreachable, uninterested, or unaware of how IP connects with OS**. This is particularly true for researchers who do not work directly with IP management or for institutions that have not yet integrated IP policies into their OS frameworks. **Vice-versa**, Open Science frameworks and practices often overlook or insufficiently address intellectual property (IP) considerations, especially in areas such as licensing, patentability, or knowledge valorisation. This disconnect can lead to uncertainty or missed opportunities when researchers engage in open dissemination without clear guidance on how to protect or strategically manage IP rights.

Another risk is **the potential for low campaign impact** if the messaging does not effectively communicate **why IP matters within OS**. To prevent this, IP4OS must **develop clear, compelling narratives and ensure its educational materials are engaging, accessible, and actionable**.

A further challenge lies in **identifying the key decision-makers within universities and research institutions who have the authority to drive change**. While researchers and knowledge transfer professionals are important stakeholders, institutional leadership—such as **vice-rectors for research, university boards, and government policymakers**—play a critical role in implementing policies that shape how IP is managed within OS. Recognising and engaging these influential figures will be essential to the campaign's success.

Finally, **the campaign's credibility depends on having strong role models and success stories**. If IP4OS is unable to showcase real-world examples of institutions and researchers successfully **balancing IP and OS**, its messaging may struggle to gain traction. Therefore, identifying and promoting impactful role models and **successful case studies** will be critical to the campaign strategy.

4.5. Conclusions

The IP4OS initiative has a strong foundation, leveraging a **multi-channel approach, carefully selected role models, and existing IP and OS networks**, along with EU initiatives and campaigns outlined in section 4.1. However, **challenges such as fragmented stakeholder engagement, the lack of clear KPIs, and limited IP visibility in OS policies and institutional practice** need to be addressed strategically.

To maximise its impact, IP4OS must **develop precise engagement strategies, learn from successful global OS initiatives, and actively collaborate with international research councils and science academies**. At the same time, **potential threats—including difficulties in reaching key stakeholders, securing institutional support, and identifying compelling success stories—must be mitigated through targeted outreach, policy engagement, and storytelling efforts**.

By carefully navigating these challenges and opportunities, **IP4OS will contribute to R&I ecosystem where IP and OS coexist in a way that fosters responsible knowledge sharing, economic growth, and societal impact**.

5. Plan of Action: Strategy & Tactics

This Role Model Campaign (see WP3, T3.1) will leverage multiple communication channels, including videos, blog posts, roadmaps, checklists, posters, flyers, and social media carousels (see WP3, T3.5). This initiative aims to engage diverse research sectors and IP4OS target stakeholders by:

1. Emphasising the benefits of agile IP management for OS.
2. Fostering collaboration among researchers, policymakers, and key stakeholders.
3. Showcasing effective IP management practices linked to OS through existing frameworks and innovative initiatives.

Aligned with WP2, these efforts will enhance knowledge sharing and complement field analysis. The campaign will also facilitate informal learning, reinforcing the training provided in WP4. Through various activities, it aims to ensure broad outreach and build a **Community of Practice (CoP)** via events, collaborations, joint knowledge initiatives, and advocacy for relevant policies (see WP3, T3.2–T3.4).

Several European entities, including the **European Commission Directorate General for Research and Innovation, EISMEA, EUIPO**, have initiated cooperation on IP management. Their efforts focus on awareness-raising activities, supporting innovative SMEs, and sharing IP-related data. IP4OS builds upon these co-creational results to identify best practices for a synergetic IP-OS approach (see WP3, T3.1).

To ensure a wide-reaching and diverse audience, IP4OS aligns with WP2 engagement strategies and extends them within WP3. It will utilise key industry events such as the **Hannover Messe Digital Edition** and platforms like the **Horizon Results Platform TV (HRP TV)**, attended by EURICE. Additionally, webinars on IP management in EU-funded projects, **Freedom to Operate**, and **IP & Artificial Intelligence**, conducted by the consortium, will serve as exchange points. **Public webinars facilitated by MIK**, as well as numerous events on the [IP4OS Roadmap](#) focused primarily on awareness-raising activities, will further contribute to this effort. Presentations and awareness-raising sessions at conferences, such as **MetaScience**, will also play a key role in engaging the audience.

WP3 will highlight **role models, key figures, and data** on agile IP management as defined in the **Synergy Framework**, fostering a **CoP through active engagement** (see WP3, T3.2) across industry, academia, and multidisciplinary professionals.

These tasks (T3.2; T3.3) will support advocates of a synergetic IP-OS approach, with a strong focus on practical implementation— a fundamental element of the Role Model Campaign. Post-campaign feedback sheets will assess the growth of awareness within the CoP, ensuring measurable impact.

5.1. Strengthening Stakeholder Engagement across different Target Groups

To ensure the success of IP4OS, it is essential to establish strong connections with key decision-makers in universities, research institutions, and funding agencies. A significant challenge in many organisations—whether publicly funded or private—is the absence of a

clear strategy for integrating intellectual property (IP) within open science (OS) policies. Thus, identifying and engaging individuals with the authority to support and implement IP4OS principles is crucial, regardless of the type of organisation. Whether within universities and public research organisations or in the private sector, this approach helps bridge the gap between IP management and open science objectives.

5.3.1. Identification of the Target Groups

To ensure a broad and inclusive outreach, IP4OS engages a diverse audience, aligning with WP2 and further leveraged in WP3. The initiative brings together a wide range of stakeholders from academia, research, industry, policymaking, and research management, fostering a **Community of Practice (CoP)** for agile IP-OS strategies.

Key Stakeholders in the IP4OS Community of Practice

- **IP and OS Stakeholders**
 - Researchers, administrators from higher education institutions (HEIs), public and private research-performing organisations (RPOs).
 - Library and information services, scholarly publishers, industry partners.
 - Policymakers, research managers, ethics committees, and funding agencies.

- **IP Stakeholders**
 - Knowledge and Technology transfer offices (KTTOs) and university departments managing IP and commercialisation.
 - Legal representatives from universities and research organisations specialising on IPRs.
 - Law firms specialising in IP, patent offices, public beneficiaries (e.g., vaccine-related initiatives).
 - IP consultants and advisors.

 - Entrepreneurships and research manager.

- **OS Stakeholders**
 - Law firms advising on OS policies and legal implications.
 - Digital repository specialists, science communicators, and journalists.
 - Open-access publishers, citizen science representatives.
 - Data protection officers.
 - Funders (DFG, EC with H2020/E) opposing OS obligations on new projects.
 - Policymakers (ERA-authors).
 - OS representatives in academia: librarians, researchers/reproducibility networks.

5.3.2. Categorisation of Target Groups

IP4OS structures its target groups into three primary categories:

- Group A: IP Experts and Intermediaries**
 Professionals involved in knowledge and technology transfer, data management, and research policy, such as Knowledge and Technology Transfer (KTT) professionals, research managers, and policymakers.
- Group B: Experts Performing Research**
 Researchers and organisations from both public and private sectors who need effective IP management for their projects, including innovation managers, research students, and spin-off/start-up innovators.
- Group C: Trainers and Multipliers**
 Academic lecturers, teaching librarians, and professional advisors responsible for disseminating IP and OS knowledge within educational and professional settings.

By engaging these diverse groups, the campaign fosters collaboration, knowledge sharing, and advocacy, ensuring a stronger, more integrated approach to IP-OS implementation.

Table 1: IP4OS Target groups and their level of knowledge, skills, awareness and advocacy for IP and/or OS (see p.11 of Part B of the DoA in the GA).

Target Group	Sub-group	No.	Representatives	Level of awareness, skills, advocacy for
Group A. IP experts and intermediaries		1	KTT Professionals	X X X
		2	Infrastructure providing stakeholders in the EU R&I system (e.g. RFOs, RPOs, Publishers, Companies working on science communication & dissemination in EU projects)	X X X
		3	Entrepreneurship Officers	XX
		4	Research Librarians	X X X
		5	Data Managers / Data Stewards	XX
		6	Research Managers	XX
		7	Policymakers (as promoters and supporters of scientific messages and tools)	X
Group B. Experts performing research (in need of IA management for their work/projects)	B1 active in the public sector	8	OS Ambassadors	X X X
		9	Researchers*	X
		10	Research students**	X
		11	Academic and University lecturers	X
		12	Innovation Managers in Industry & SMEs (collaborating with public sector)	XX
	B2 active in the private sector	13	RPO's professional, managerial, and/or academic staff	XX
		3	Entrepreneurship Officers	XX
		8	OS Ambassadors	X X X
		13	RPO's professional, managerial, and/or academic staff	XX
		12	Innovation Managers in Industry & SMEs	XX
Group C. Trainers in IP or research		14	Innovators from Spin-Offs and Start-Ups	XX
		9	Researchers*	XX
		1	KTT Professionals	X X X
		8	OS Ambassadors	X X X
		15	Teaching Librarians	X X X
		13	RPO's professional, managerial, and/or academic staff	XX
	3	Entrepreneurship Officers	XX	
	11	Academic and University lecturers	X	

5.3.3. Stakeholder Engagement

Stakeholder Engagement for the Synergy Framework is designed to engage closely with key stakeholders from the IP and OS sectors to assess their needs and inform and enhance the development of a comprehensive framework. This will include reaching out to stakeholders via the consortium networks, organising multi-professional dialogues and workshops for in depth engagement, and analysing feedback for integration into the framework. The Collaboration between WP2, 3 and 4 ensures stakeholder insights are effectively incorporated into the broader project objectives. WP5 supports WP2, 3, and 4 with dissemination activities. The anticipated outputs are a comprehensive stakeholder engagement in the draft of the Synergy Framework, reflecting the integrated stakeholder recommendations and best practices (see WP2, T.2.2.).

At the university level, the **first step** is mapping out **the key institutional figures** responsible for research strategy and funding distribution. These figures often include **vice-rectors for research, heads of knowledge technology transfer offices, and legal advisors specialising in IP**. Their endorsement and support will drive policy changes within academic institutions.

For further institutional engagement as well as wider dissemination of a synergetic IP-OS approach among institutions, IP4OS will establish multi-professional teams in 27 countries that will act as representatives and consultants within their respective organisations. These multi-professionals are individuals with experience in knowledge **technology transfer, publication and licensing, research management or administration, OS, research ethics and/or legal affairs** who can advocate for the benefits of integrating IP awareness into OS practices and policies.

At the policy level, engaging **research funding agencies** and **policymakers** is equally important (see WP3, T.3.4). Many funding bodies now require OS compliance, but they often lack specific IP guidelines. IP4OS will work towards facilitating **direct dialogues with funding agencies** and **policymakers** to emphasise the importance of incorporating clear IP guidance within their funding conditions.

Additionally, IP4OS will **collaborate with data-sharing platforms** that are already established within the European research ecosystem (Zenodo) and beyond (OSF). Besides being an important stakeholder group for licensing and OS practices, these platforms can serve as channels for disseminating IP4OS materials and promoting good practices among researchers who are actively engaged in initiatives dealing with IP and OS.

5.2. Making IP4OS visible through Digital & Media Strategies

For IP4OS to have a lasting impact, it must leverage multiple digital and media channels to reach its target audiences effectively. The campaign will be structured around a **multi-platform approach**, utilising **social media** (LinkedIn, Bluesky), **online publications** (resource collection at the IP4OS website, IP4OS YouTube channel, Zenodo and OSF), and **webinars** organised by WP3 and which will be showcased in the news sections of the IP4OS website, IP4OS YouTube channel, Zenodo, and OSF to engage stakeholders (see WP5, T5.4, M1-M24).

A key component of this strategy is **producing high-quality and accessible content** that explains the complexities of IP and OS and its synergies in a user-friendly manner. This includes:

- A **series of blog posts** that address key issues such as **the intersection of IP and OS, challenges in data sharing, and real-world case studies**.
- **Targeted media articles** (such as news about current events) will be published in prominent research and policy journals, highlighting **how researchers and institutions can unpack possibilities with IP and OS**.
- **Infographics and video explainers** that break down key concepts and provide step-by-step guides on IP management within OS frameworks.
- **teaser video** announcing the IP4OS summit/workshops/training sessions.
- **Press releases, news items, regular e-newsletters**, and a constant **social media environment** at the time of implementation.

Social media engagement will play a crucial role in increasing IP4OS's reach. The campaign should focus on **LinkedIn and Bluesky** as primary platforms, where discussions on research policy and innovation are most active. The use of **dedicated hashtags**, such as **#IP4Innovation** and **#ResponsibleIP**, will help consolidate conversations and drive greater engagement.

Furthermore, IP4OS will actively participate in **major European research conferences and OS events** (Such as the Conferences organised by EARMA, Metascience, IFIA, OASPA, EOSC and many more, see IP4OS Roadmap on the IP4OS Whiteboard) where it can present its findings, host panel discussions, and engage directly with key stakeholders for awareness-raising activities and project results dissemination. Establishing a presence at these events will enhance the project's credibility and encourage broader adoption of its recommendations.

Final materials will be published on the IP4OS website and available for download and professional printing (open access) under CC licenses. In a synchronised announcement, the launch of these materials will also be shared via press releases, media coverage, newsletters, and social media. Ensuring sustainability, they will remain accessible on the IP4OS website and European Knowledge Valorisation Platform even after the project's completion. An overview of the developed and disseminated campaign materials will be provided in D3.1 in M20 (led by PENSOFT). The campaign's impact (50 % awareness raise) will be assessed via qualitative feedback in T1.4 and T1.6.

5.3. Raise Dialogue & Strategic Insights

The IP4OS website will serve as an IP4OS Digital Platform for Community of Practice Engagement (see WP3, T3.2, M7-M20). The IP4OS website will be used for resources, discussions, and collaborations. This platform will host webinars with experts discussing various aspects of IP in OS. Topics could include “Navigating IP in Collaborative Research”, “IP Management for Startups”, “Understanding Patents in the OS Ecosystem”, “IP Management in EU-funded Projects”, “IP and Artificial Intelligence”, and “Freedom to Operate in Research”.

IP4OS will also design and implement **Open Innovation Challenges** (see WP3, T3.3., M7-M20). These challenges will bring together participants from different jurisdictions, enabling them to collaborate in multidisciplinary teams to address real-world scientific

challenges using OS principles. These initiatives will serve as role models for open and collaborative research by showcasing successful case studies. IP4OS will integrate representatives of the EPO and EUIPO into the CoP (see WP3, T3.3 and T3.4) due to their crucial roles in granting, managing, and applying IPR in Europe.

To drive systemic change, IP4OS will actively engage with policymakers, advocating for integrating agile IP management complementing OS practices in research (see WP3, T.3.4, M12-M23). This approach fosters innovation and strengthens the adoption of OS principles. By highlighting good practices and success stories, we aim to position adaptable IP tools as a key enabler of scientific progress. IP4OS will start with the “General Guidelines on Responsible Open Science” (H20220 ROSIE).

IP4OS will facilitate high-level discussions among researchers, industry leaders, social innovation pioneers, and policymakers. A flagship initiative under this strategy will be the European Research (**IP4OS**) **Summit** in Brussels, organised by WP3, which will convene 50 key stakeholders. These roundtables will serve as a platform for exchanging insights and driving policy alignment between innovation ecosystems and regulatory frameworks (see WP3, T3.4.1).

IP4OS will develop and distribute targeted policy briefs and a comprehensive white paper to sustain momentum and ensure long-term impact. These documents will advocate for policies that support a harmonised and strategic approach to IP and OS, providing policymakers with actionable recommendations to foster an open and innovation-driven research landscape (see WP3, T3.4.2).

5.4. Train-the-Trainer Programme

Throughout months 12 to 24, IP4OS will offer high-quality interactive training sessions, implementing the **IP4OS Train-the-Trainer Programme** for multi-professional teams (see WP4, T4.2). This task will train multipliers for multi-professional teams in all 27 European Countries with IP4OS train-the-trainer approach for multi-professional teams. This reach is possible to the partner’s already existing training networks. Additionally, IP4OS will train 300 professionals with extensive coverage of IP topics, including those untouched by existing initiatives. The partners CAU, MIK, ASTP, UZSM and EURICE will deliver sessions ensuring a versatile learning experience.

6. Monitoring & Evaluating the Impact of the IP4OS Campaign

To measure the success of the IP4OS Campaign, key messages for each stakeholder group will be identified and utilised for communication and dissemination purposes. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) will be set to ensure effective monitoring of each action’s progress (see WP5, T.5.2).

Therefore, the following preliminary Timeline and KPI’s for both during and after the project were established as follows (see also T6: IP4OS CDE actions, tools and KPI’s of the Grant Agreement). This Table will be refined in D5.2 (M6):

Table 2: IP4OS CDE actions, tools and KPI's (see p. 17 of Part B of the DoA in the GA)

C/D/E	Tool	KPIs for project duration
C	promotional materials	≥4 materials; ≥700 downloads; utilised at ≥8 events
C&D	IP4OS website & blog	≥25 news items; ≥4 blog posts; ≥30 documents in library; ≥5.000 visits; ≥120 sec. av. session
C&D	Press release	≥4 press releases; ≥6.000 views
C&D	E-newsletter	≥4 issues; ≥150 subscribers; >35% open rate; >20% linkclick rate; <10% unsubscribe rate; >150 downloads from website
C&D	Social media networks	200 (re)posts; 300 followers; 75.000 impressions; 800 users traffic to website
C&D	Media broadcast local level	Interviews/radio/TV broadcast>5
C&D	Video	≥3 videos; ≥800 views
D	Academic publications	≥4 publications
D	Public deliverables	≥11 deliverables available on website; ≥50 downloads each
D	Presentations at events	>10 international & national events where the project was presented e.g. in organised sessions; >1000 total participants at the events
D&E	Success Stories	3 testimonials from T1.4
D&E	Webinar Series	≥4, 100 attendees
D&E	Legacy booklet	≥300 views
D&E	IP4OS role model material	10 posters, 2 videos, 50 social media posts reaching 25000 people
E	Training Centre	≥ 27 train-the-trainer sessions + ≥300 IP management course users
E	Policy briefs	≥2 policy briefs; ≥500 views; available on ≥2 platforms
E	Submission of opinions to open calls for evidence	≥2 submissions provided that relevant calls are open during the project's duration
E	IP4OS summit	150 attendees

Feedback from stakeholders will be collected through feedback sheets (see WP4, T.4.3), as well as qualitative insights on IP4OS empowerment from each European country via the **EURICE** ambassador network using the **CAUs** online tool **Qualtrics** (see WP1, T.1.4 and 1.6). This process will continuously inform and refine the programme, ensuring it remains dynamic and relevant. Additionally, a **data-driven evaluation of engagement metrics** will help refine future outreach efforts.

IP4OS will establish a **gender-sensitive feedback mechanism** (see WP4, T.4.3) to ensure that the strategies are responsive to the fluctuating requirements of the IP4OS CoP (WP1, T1.4).

By ensuring continuous monitoring and adaptation, IP4OS will remain responsive to the needs of its target audience and drive lasting changes in how IP is managed within the OS landscape.

IP4OS will ensure the project's long-term impact and sustainability by enshrining the Synergy Framework (WP2), the Synergy Core Curriculum (WP4) and campaign materials (WP3) on pertinent platforms, for example, the Knowledge Valorisation Platform, EU Innovation Radar Platform, Open Research Europe and EOSC, the European IP Helpdesk and the Embassy Of Good Science to ascertain the project's long-term viability and effect (see WP5, T.5.3, M18-M24).

IP4OS will develop and distribute targeted policy briefs and a comprehensive white paper to sustain momentum and ensure long-term impact (WP3, T3.4.2, M9, lead by **MIK**). These documents will advocate for policies that support a synergetic and strategic approach to IP and OS, providing policymakers with actionable recommendations to foster an open and innovation-driven research landscape.

7. Implementation Plan

Phase 1: Preparation & Strategic Alignment (Months 1-3)

- **Establish Core Objectives:** Define key messages, goals, and success indicators for the campaign.
- **Stakeholder Mapping:** Identify and categorise target groups (researchers, policymakers, industry, etc.).
- **Resource Allocation:** Assign roles within the consortium for content creation, outreach, and engagement.
- **Platform & Channel Selection:** Confirm communication channels (HRP TV, social media, webinars, conferences, etc.).
- **Develop Initial Content:** Create draft materials such as blog post outlines, video scripts, and social media strategies.

Phase 2: Content Development & Engagement Setup (Months 3-20)

- **Content Creation:**
 - Develop high-quality blog posts, videos, checklists, posters, and flyers.
 - Produce infographics and explainers on IP-OS synergies.
 - Design a **teaser video** announcing upcoming events.

- **CoP Establishment:**
 - Launch digital forums on the IP4OS website for discussion and networking.
 - Initiate outreach to key industry and academic figures to engage as role models.
- **Strategic Event Planning:**
 - Confirm participation in major industry events (e.g. Hannover Messe, HRP TV).
 - Organise initial webinars on topics such as **IP Management for OS**.

Phase 3: Campaign Launch & Public Engagement (Months 4-12)

- **Official Campaign Kickoff:**
 - Simultaneous launch of materials across digital platforms.
 - Press releases and media outreach to raise awareness.
 - Social media push with dedicated hashtags (#IP4Innovation, #ResponsibleIP).
- **Community of Practice (CoP) Activation:**
 - Host interactive discussions and Q&A sessions with role models.
 - Encourage stakeholders to share case studies and best practices.
- **Open Innovation Challenges:**
 - Launch cross-disciplinary competitions for IP-OS problem-solving.
 - Facilitate collaboration between researchers, industry, and policymakers.

Phase 4: Knowledge Sharing & Advocacy (Months 4-24)

- **Stakeholder Engagement Expansion:**
 - Strengthen ties with the European Commission, EISMEA, and EUIPO.
 - Collaborate with research funding agencies on IP integration into OS policies.
- **Training & Education Support (Months 7-24):**
 - Organise professional development workshops on IP and OS.
 - Provide guidance to universities and research institutions on best practices.
 - Conduct IP training and implement the IP4OS Train-the-Trainer Programme for multiprofessional teams.
- **Policy Advocacy (Months 12-23)**
 - Roundtable Discussions with Policymakers
 - IP4OS Summit in Brussels with 50 guests.
- **White Paper Development (Months 20-23):**
 - Gather insights from the campaign to draft policy recommendations.
 - Advocate for structured support for IP-OS integration.

Phase 5: Impact Assessment & Sustainability (Months 20-24)

- **Post-Campaign Feedback Collection:**
 - Conduct feedback and surveys to measure awareness growth within the CoP.
 - Analyse engagement metrics from webinars, digital platforms, and events.
- **Final Report & Policy Briefs:**
 - Publish a comprehensive report on campaign outcomes.
 - Distribute policy briefs to research institutions and policymakers.
- **Long-Term Integration:**
 - Ensure materials remain accessible on the IP4OS website.
 - Maintain dialogue with stakeholders to continue fostering IP-OS synergies.

8. Conclusion

The Role Model Campaign is a pivotal initiative in ensuring the successful adoption of agile IP strategies complementing OS. By leveraging role models, knowledge-sharing platforms, and targeted engagement efforts, IP4OS will drive systemic change, fostering a research landscape where IP supports OS. The campaign’s impact will be sustained through strategic policy integration, stakeholder commitment, and continuous monitoring of outreach effectiveness.

Figure 1: Role Model Campaign Poster